

Coupling of the Monte Carlo Code Serpent with the CTF Subchannel Code on a VVER440 mini-core

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DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.20803472

ABSTRACT

In many cases, validation must rely on code-to-code comparisons using high-fidelity models as reference. The paper presents the development of a coupling between the subchannel code CTF and the Monte Carlo code Serpent for hexagonal geometries. For this purpose, the existing coupling interfaces of each code are used. To facilitate the data exchange, a Python library was developed to automatically generate the mapping tables required by CTF. The coupling is verified on the VVER440 mini-core exercise from the C5G7-TD benchmark. Steady-state convergence was reached. A power level was identified which results in thermal-hydraulic conditions close to nominal reaction conditions despite the large power gradient.

Keywords: Monte Carlo, subchannel code, high-fidelity coupling, VVER440

1. INTRODUCTION

The experimental validation of thermal-hydraulics/neutronics multi-physics coupled system is challenging, particularly for high resolution (i.e. pin-by-pin) models since measurements in nuclear power plants usually provide assembly-wise power distributions. In the case of new reactor types, measurements do not exist yet. For such cases, validation must rely on code-to-code comparison using high-order models as reference. For neutronics, Monte Carlo codes often serve as a reference since they solve the neutron transport equation without any assumption or simplification. Moreover, they can easily deal with complex geometries. Previously reserved for the simulation of stationary states, Monte Carlo codes are increasingly used also for time-dependent applications, both for slow (e.g. depletion) and for fast (e.g. transient) processes. For thermal-hydraulics, CFD codes offer the highest resolution but their limitations in terms of application (e.g. simulation of 2-phase flow) as well as in computational cost, limit their practical use. Thermal-hydraulics subchannel codes are therefore often preferred for coupled applications since they present a good compromise between high resolution at the pin level and computational cost [1].

GRS is developing the neutron transport calculation code FENNECS [2], based on the finite element method, and capable of resolving the power distribution at the pin level. Its coupling with the subchannel code CTF [3] is planned, which necessitates a reference solution for the verification/validation. Addressing this need, the development of a coupling between the subchannel code CTF and the Monte Carlo code Serpent [4] is the objective of the current work. In this paper, the CTF and Serpent codes and their respective coupling interfaces are briefly described in the next section. The coupling approach is presented in Section 3. Finally, the results of the coupled code system applied to the VVER440 mini-core exercise from the C5G7-TD benchmark [5] are presented.

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2. CODES DESCRIPTION

2.1. Serpent

Serpent [4] is a Monte Carlo neutron and photon transport code, it can be applied for various reactor physics, fusion neutronics, and radiation transport applications. The code is developed as part of the Kraken multi-physics computational framework at VTT Technical Research Centre of Finland. The code documentation including a description of the multi-physics interface can be freely accessed in [6].

The geometry of a Serpent model is described using a set of non-overlapping regions, each filled with a material. In the simplest case, the material properties are constant in space and time. For the purposes of a coupled calculation, the spatial distribution of the material temperature and density can be defined on a spatial mesh independently from the model geometry. The mesh description is stored in a separate file which can be easily read, written or updated by an external program. When the material properties are defined in a mesh, Serpent calculates powers in pins and then distributes it to the elements of the mesh, to provide e.g. the feedback to the coupled TH code.

The Serpent interface provides various mesh type files which can be used depending on the application. They can be divided in a few categories: point-average, regular mesh, fuel behavior and unstructured mesh. For the present application (a VVER440 mini-core), the discretization method best suited for defining the density and temperature for each pin is the nested hexagonal regular mesh, since it fits the fuel assembly and pin geometrical structure exactly. The unstructured mesh could also be used, however its definition is much more convoluted, since it requires description of every mesh element corresponding to each separate pin.

2.2. CTF

CTF [3] is a version of the subchannel thermal-hydraulics code COBRA-TF (COolant Boiling in Bundle Array – Two Fluid) jointly developed at ORNL and NCSU.

Over the years, CTF has been coupled to several neutronics codes. At GRS, CTF was coupled to the inhouse diffusion solver QUABOX/CUBBOX [7] and with the discrete ordinates transport code TORT-TD [8]. Currently, a coupling between CTF and FENNECS, focused on pin-by-pin applications is being developed.

The coupling interface with Serpent, developed at NCSU [9] has several special features. CTF calls the Serpent executable and has no access to Serpent's internal variables. Therefore, the exchange of data takes place, not through direct memory exchange, but through the interface files that Serpent is able to read and generate. In order to correctly interpret and write the Serpent interface files, so-called mapping table files are required as additional input.

3. COUPLING METHOD

3.1. Automatic Generation of the Mapping Tables

As mentioned in the previous section, three different “mapping table” files are needed by the CTF interface. The first table contains the coolant mapping, which is provided with 4 columns as shown in (1). Given the coolant-centered modelling approach in CTF, this is the only table in which the weighting factors differ from 1.0. E.g. for a pin surrounded by 6 channels, the weighting factor is $1/6=0.167$.

$$CTF \text{ Channel ID, CTF Axial Node, Serpent Cell ID, Weighting Factor} \quad (1)$$

The second table contains the fuel rod mapping (for Doppler temperature exchange), which is also provided with 4 columns as in (2). It is important to note that at the moment the cladding temperature is assumed to be the same as the coolant.

$$CTF \text{ Rod ID, CTF Axial Node, Serpent Cell ID, Weighting Factor} \quad (2)$$

The third table contains the power mapping, which is also provided with 4 columns as in (3). At a first glance, (2) and (3) seem equivalent but the Serpent ID refers to the pin object and not the cell.

$$CTF \text{ Power ID, CTF Axial Node, Serpent Pin ID, Weighting Factor} \quad (3)$$

In order to automatically generate the mapping tables, a Python library was developed. The program reads the Serpent input of the model and writes the mapping tables. Several assumptions are made: the Serpent model uses nested regular meshes, and in the CTF model, the channels, their order and topology follow the logic of the hexagonal preprocessor developed during the NURES SAFE project. [10] Finally, the same axial discretization is used.

3.2. Coupling Algorithm

Using the interface developed at NCSU [9], the coupling is activated in CTF by using a flag in the command line. The Serpent executable is called from the CTF interface thus allowing both codes to retain their steady-state capabilities. After the initialization of both codes, the CTF model is run with the power profile contained in the input to provide initial feedback distribution for Serpent. An iterative process follows of each code converging internally before exchanging data through the files.

To help convergence, a dynamic relaxation factor can be applied to the TH parameters from CTF following the formulas (4) and (5). For the power, a constant relaxation coefficient of 0.5 is applied.

$$Feedback(n) = Feedback(n - 1) \times (1 - RelDyn) - Feedback(n) \times RelDyn \quad (4)$$

where:

$$RelDyn = 1.0 - 0.7 \times e^{\frac{-1.0}{max_rel_linf}} \quad (5)$$

where max_rel_linf is the maximum relative change of feedback parameter from one iteration to the next.

The CTF interface also allows to define the Doppler correlation (6) applied for the effective temperature transferred to Serpent.

$$T_{Doppler} = A \times T_{Average} + B \times T_{Centerline} + C \times T_{Surface} \quad (6)$$

The Chabert-Santamarina correlation [11] is selected, where A = 1.0, B = -0.055 and C = 0.055.

4. VERIFICATION ON THE C5G7-TD BENCHMARK

4.1. Benchmark Description

The C5G7-TD benchmark [5] from the OECD/NEA was recently extended to include hexagonal assembly cases. This study focuses on the mini-core loaded with fuel elements of the VVER440 type. These assembly types are endowed with a wrapper around the fuel bundle, thus preventing coolant exchange between the fuel bundles. A graphical representation of the mini-core can be found in Figure 1. The core contains 19 fuel assemblies with 3 different enrichments surrounded by a layer of reflector assemblies containing only water. All fuel assembly types contain 126 fuel pins and a central instrumentation tube. Type #2 assemblies, which have the highest enrichment, also feature 6 fuel pins containing burnable absorber (Gadolinium). These pins are clearly identifiable in the power distribution provided in Figure 4.

The first phase of the benchmark only features single-physics exercises, but the second phase will include coupled cases with thermal-hydraulics feedback. In addition to verifying the validity of the coupling, this study aims at providing a first coupled case to help identify a power level for which the thermal-hydraulics conditions remain reasonably close to nominal conditions in a real reactor. i.e. no boiling, fuel temperatures far from the melting point.

4.2. Neutronics Model

The geometry as well as the material definitions are taken from the benchmark specifications [5]. The Serpent model uses nested regular meshes. In the pin-by-pin fuel assembly, the flat face is perpendicular to the x-axis, whereas in the core lattices the flat face is perpendicular to the y-axis. This is the same representation used in Figure 4 and 6. For the axial direction, 30 axial layers are defined

directly in the interface files since the Serpent model only differentiates axial layers by material definition. The selected number of neutrons per generation and of active generations are 100000 and 700 respectively. Forty inactive generations are simulated. In this way, a relative uncertainty of below 0.02 % is achieved for keff in the individual Serpent calculations. The ENDF/B.VII.1 nuclear data library is used.

4.3. TH Model

The CTF subchannel model was generated using the preprocessor previously mentioned in section 3.1. A coolant-centered approach is used. Following the coolant-centered modelling, several approaches are possible for the modelling of the bundle corner. The selected option, using two trapezoids and a total of four channels surrounding the corner pin is displayed in Figure 2. This results in a total of 252 channels for each assembly. The water in the central guide tube is not modelled and is kept constant at inlet temperature in Serpent. Because of the wrapper surrounding the fuel assemblies, no mass exchange between bundles is possible and thus no cross-connections are modelled. Similarly, no heat transfer is considered between assemblies in CTF. This will allow for easier use of the CTF parallelization option which is based on domain decomposition.

4.4. Results Analysis

4.4.1. Convergence of the coupled solution

With the L-2 convergence criteria set to $1.0e-2$ for the coolant temperature, coolant density, fuel surface temperature, fuel centerline temperature and the linear power distribution, the coupled calculation reached convergence after 265 iterations between Serpent and CTF. The coupled calculation lasted about 165 hours, with 48 threads used for the Serpent OpenMP parallelization. Figure 3 shows the convergence of the L2 norm for the linear power distribution, which is the limiting criterion. Although the parameter decreases fast during the first iterations, going from $1.0e-1$ to $1.0e-2$ takes several 100 iterations. It could be due to the statistical uncertainties from the Serpent model itself. Sensitivity studies will be performed to find an optimum for runtime between the statistics of the Monte Carlo model and the number of coupled iterations.

Figure 2. Channel/rods numbering of a VVER440 assembly model in CTF

Figure 3. Convergence of the relative L2-normalized 3D power (logarithmic scales)

4.4.2. Steady-state results

The results presented thereafter correspond to a total core power of 29.4 MW. At the end of the steady-state convergence, to achieve $k_{eff} = 1.0$, Serpent uses the "set iter" parameter to determine a scaling factor of 0.153. Multiplying the initial boron atomic number densities by this factor results in the critical boron concentration of 92 ppm.

Figure 4 shows the 2D pin power distribution at the end of the convergence process in layer 15 in which the peaking of the axial power distribution is observed. The central assembly has a higher power level and a homogeneous distribution. However, the maximum pin power is reached in the first ring of fuel assemblies which have the highest enrichment. The power maximum is reached in the pins directly next to the central assembly. In those assemblies, the minimum power is also observed in a pin containing burnable absorbers. The assemblies in the second ring all have low power level due to the low enrichment and the high neutron leakage.

Figure 5 shows the 2D pin-by-pin distribution of the power difference between the first Serpent iteration (i.e. without any TH feedback) and the final one at the end of the convergence. A clear shift of the power distribution from the center to the edge of the minicore can be observed. This is the expected behaviour because of the negative feedback effects of both fuel and moderator temperature where the power is higher.

The 2D Doppler temperature distribution at the end of the convergence process is not shown here as it closely mirrors the power distribution. This suggests that the data exchange between CTF and Serpent is performed correctly. The maximum temperature is 825K which remains well below the fuel melting point.

Figure 6 shows the 2D moderator density distribution at the end of the convergence process in the last axial layer of model. The outlet of the core was selected as the area where the lowest moderator density (i.e. highest moderator temperature) is reached with a value of 668 kg/m^3 directly next to the pin with the peak power. No boiling is observed.

Figure 4 Pin-by-pin radial power distribution after coupled convergence

Figure 5. Difference between the first Serpent power distribution (no TH Feedback) and the final one

Figure 6. Pin-by-pin moderator density distribution after coupled convergence

5. CONCLUSIONS

The neutron transport Monte Carlo code Serpent was successfully coupled to the thermal-hydraulics subchannel code CTF. For this purpose, the existing interfaces of both codes were used. To automatize the generation of the mapping tables required by CTF, a Python package was developed. The coupling is verified using the VVER440 mini-core exercise from the C5G7-TD benchmark. A steady-state convergence was reached. A power level which allows to obtain thermal-hydraulic conditions close to nominal reaction conditions despite the large power gradient was identified. Slightly below 30 MW, the critical boron concentration remains positive (92 ppm), thus leaving some margin for a reactivity transient. No boiling is observed and the fuel temperature stays well below safety margins even in the pin with peak power.

Future work will include the parallelization of the CTF model and convergence acceleration of the coupled system. The system will be used as a reference to validate the newly developed FENNECS/CTF coupled system.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

The work presented here was supported in part by the German federal ministry for the Environment, Nature Conservation, Nuclear Safety and Consumer Protection (Contract ID. 4721R01335)

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